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Evaluation of Enrollees' Perspectives on the Operations of the National Health Insurance Scheme in Nigeria

Oluwaseye O Adesokun¹, Kanayo P Osemene², Matthew O Ilori³, Romanus M Ihekoronye⁴

¹ Obafemi Awolowo University Health Centre, Ile-Ife, Osun State, Nigeria

^{2,4} Department of Clinical Pharmacy & Pharmacy Administration, Faculty of Pharmacy, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Osun State, Nigeria.

³ African Institute for Science Policy and Innovation, Faculty of Technology, Obafemi, Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Osun State, Nigeria.

Correspondence: Kanayo P Osemene, Department of Clinical Pharmacy & Pharmacy Administration, Faculty of Pharmacy, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Osun State, Nigeria, E-mail: osemenekanayo@gmail.com
Phone No. +234(08) 37161268

Abstract

Background: The National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS) was established in 2005 to act as an alternative source of funding for health care services but marred with operational problems. **Objective:** The study examined the mode of operation of the NHIS and assessed its adequacy to achieve set objectives in the face of contending factors from the point of view of enrollees. **Methods:** A descriptive cross-sectional survey of 300 enrollees in three tertiary health facilities in Southwestern Nigeria was undertaken between August and October, 2019. Participants were selected using a combination of quota and simple random sampling methods. Primary data were obtained using semi-structured questionnaires and focus group discussions. Frequency, percentages, weighted means and relative importance indices were used to analyse data at $p < 0.05$ level of significance. **Results:** Response rate for both focus groups and questionnaires was 100%. Mean age of respondents was 43.11 years while that of focus groups discussants was 40.81 years. Enrollees understood the objectives of the NHIS and its components especially its focus on improving service efficiency (85%). However, they posit that the mode of operations was inadequate to accomplish those goals. Factors identified as responsible for this include capacity limitations in terms of infrastructure (89%), human resources (84%), and financial resources (66%); corruption (65%) as well as poor responsiveness by service providers (44%). **Conclusion:** Enrollees in the NHIS in Nigeria understand the goals of the scheme even though more enlightenment is needed to drive home the philosophy. The mode of operations is inadequate to achieve the objectives of the scheme. Reforms are needed to address inadequacies in infrastructure, capacities and management of services.

Keywords: National Health Insurance Scheme; Healthcare Services, Nigeria

Introduction

The National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS) in Nigeria was established in 2005 to provide universal coverage to Nigerians via social health insurance by providing a sustainable alternative source of funding for health care services. Nigeria is a federation of 36 semi-autonomous States with a federal capital territory in Abuja. There are 774 local government areas. Health is a joint responsibility of the federal, state, and local governments. The Federal government owns and manages the public-sector tertiary health care facilities; the states are responsible for secondary health facilities while the local governments are responsible for the primary health care centres across the country. The federal government sets the health agenda and gives policy directives to guide the health sector in Nigeria (Federal Ministry of Health Nigeria. 2014). The NHIS is one such policy initiative.

The NHIS is a social safety arrangement that provides financial security to the populace against unanticipated ill health. The formal sector workers, informal sector workers as well as the vulnerable groups are covered by the scheme programmes (NHIS, 2012; Mohammed, 2015). Contributions for NHIS are earnings-related. The employer pays 10% while the employee pays 5%, representing 15% of the employee's basic salary. However, the employer may choose to pay the whole contribution. The employee, a spouse and four biological children under the age of 18 years are covered by the healthcare benefits from the contributions. More children or dependents exceeding the age of 18 years on NHIS principal beneficiary could be covered on the payment of extra contributions by the principal beneficiary. The package is comprehensively planned to cover most of the health care needs of Nigerians (Odeyemi & Nixon. 2013).

There are five major stakeholders in the scheme; namely Employer, Employee, Health Care Provider (Primary and Secondary), Health Maintenance Organization (HMO) (the operators of the scheme) and the Government Agency -NHIS (Ministry of Health 2013). Employees of the federal civil service are automatically entitled to healthcare under the NHIS. However, to participate in the scheme, contributors will first register with an NHIS-approved HMO and thereafter register with a primary health care provider of their choice from an approved list of providers registered by their HMO. The contributor and his/her dependents are issued identification (ID) card at registration. In the event of sickness, the ID card entitles the insured person; his/her spouse and four children under the age of 18 years to full health benefits (Ministry of Health 2013).

Health care providers under the scheme are rewarded either by capitation or fee-for service rendered. Capitation is the payment to a primary health care provider by the Health Maintenance Organisations (HMOs) on behalf of a contributor. This is done monthly whether or not the services are accessed. Fee-for service is made by HMOs to non-capitation receiving health care providers who deliver services on referral from other health care providers (Adekola 2015). When a registered beneficiary (enrollee) in a health facility uses some form of health care, such person does not require cash to access the necessary treatment, except the 10% co-payment for the cost of drugs. In this manner, it prevents the normal practice of exchanging properties to cash for payment of health care services (catastrophic health expenditure). A 2013 report indicated that Nigeria had the highest out-of-pocket payment and the worst health indicators in the world (Gustafsson-Wright & Schellekens 2013). Reversing this trend must first address a number of challenges- from inadequate and poorly equipped health facilities, poor nutritional status inadequate access to affordable health care services, insufficient distribution of health care amenities, scarcity of drugs, poor thoughts of health workers, the huge cost of health services mostly out of the reach of the poor, poor infrastructure and improper health education approach (Olonade, et al.2019; Sparkes, et al. 2019).

As at February 2009, records indicate that the scheme had registered over 4 million Federal civil servants and their dependents (Agba, Ushie, & Osuchuchwu 2010). However, the services have been bedeviled with long waiting times, persistent out-of-pocket expenditures for out-of-stock medicines and supplies, corruption in the management of the scheme, poor attitudes of service providers, and inefficiencies at health care facilities, among others (Edeh & Udoikah 2015). Enrollees have been severally reported to express significant dissatisfaction with the scope, quality and management of services they receive under the NHIS, with some calling for the outright scrapping of the scheme (Edeh & Udoikah 2015; Eboh 2008; Azuogu, et al. 2016; Dutta & Charles 2013). Widespread discontent with the NHIS among consumers of healthcare seem to be justified considering that as of

2012, seven years after the commencement of the scheme, only an estimated 3% of the population of Nigeria had been covered by the scheme (Federal Government of Nigeria 1999).

From the foregoing, it seems inevitable that the NHIS must be reformed if it is to remain relevant in the quest for universal health coverage in Nigeria. Even though several stakeholders are involved in the scheme, all other participants (outside the enrollees/beneficiaries) contribute inputs and processes. The current study examined the perspectives of consumers of the health services as their opinions will provide an important calibration of the outputs of the collective efforts of all the input variables in the NHIS. The study considered enrollees' understanding of the objectives and mode of operation of the NHIS vis-a-vis the expected outcomes of the scheme.

Material and Methods

A descriptive cross-sectional study was undertaken using mixed data collection method. The study was carried out in three tertiary healthcare facilities, one from each of the States of Lagos, Ogun and Oyo in Southwestern Nigeria. These states were chosen because they are home to majority of the Health Maintenance Organisations (HMOs) with the highest registered principal enrollees or beneficiaries of the NHIS services in the country (NHIS. 2012). The Southwest zonal headquarters of NHIS is located in Ibadan, Oyo State with Lagos existing alone administratively. The study population comprised the NHIS Principal Enrollees/Beneficiaries in the three selected tertiary health facilities, namely Federal Medical Centre (FMC), Abeokuta, Ogun State; Federal Medical Centre (FMC), Ebute- Meta, Lagos State; and University College Hospital (UCH), Ibadan, Oyo State. Preliminary findings put the total population of enrollees at about 900.

In order to meet the objectives of the study, a combination of non-probabilistic and probabilistic sampling techniques was employed. First, quota sampling technique was used to select equal number of respondents (enrollees) from each tertiary healthcare facility. Sample size of 100 per facility was chosen. Simple random sampling technique was subsequently adopted to select the actual participants among the enrollees in the NHIS scheme. Seven (7) enrollees were randomly selected per facility to participate in the three Focus Group Discussions, one FGD per facility.

The study recruited enrollees who have been accessing health care services for at least one month and have visited for more than once. Beneficiaries/enrollees/patients who were 18 years old and above were included. These conditions were imposed to do away with the possibility of inability to recall and to ensure that individuals have sufficient knowledge about the services accessible under the NHIS scheme.

The study excluded individuals who were visiting for the first time, have not been accessing health care services under the NHIS or have not accessed services within the previous one month. Beneficiaries/enrollees who were below 18 years of age were excluded.

Research Instruments

Primary data were obtained using semi-structured questionnaires. Items on the instrument were developed from the policy document of the National Health Insurance Scheme (Federal Government of Nigeria 1999). The objectives of NHIS as stated in the policy document were examined. A 5-point agreement scale (strongly agree (5), agree (4), disagree (3), strongly disagree (2) and undecided (1)) was employed to assess level of awareness and satisfaction with mode of operation of NHIS by respondents. Data from questionnaires were augmented with Focus group discussions (FGDs) using an interview guide.

The questionnaires were subjected to the expert scrutiny of two senior faculty members (including the principal investigator) who had expertise in social health insurance. Their comments and corrections were used to ensure face and construct validity of the instruments. To ensure reliability of the instrument, a test-retest measurement was employed using forty (40) respondents from the Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospital Ile-Ife, Osun State. The reliability analysis gave a Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient of 0.87. (This indicated that the questionnaire was reliable as it measured the study constructs consistently).

Ethical approval (HREC No: IPHOAU/11/1024) was obtained from the Health Research Ethic Committee (HREC) of the Institute of Public Health, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife Nigeria.

Eighteen (18) research assistants were carefully recruited and trained on data collection. They were assigned in three teams of six (6) to each of the three tertiary health facilities for the purpose of questionnaire administration and collection between August 1 to October 31, 2019. An overage of 30% (that is, additional 30) was added to number of questionnaires distributed per facility to ensure 100 useable responses were collected. The researchers personally conducted the focus group discussions with selected respondents within the same time period. A dual-moderator strategy was adopted with one researcher ensuring the discussions proceeded smoothly while the second ensured all relevant topics were covered (Ogunbameru & Ogunbameru 2018). A research assistant took notes. The discussions were tape-recorded and transcribed verbatim for data analysis. All respondents gave their informed consents in writing.

Data obtained from the instruments was carefully sorted, coded, and cross-checked for data management using Excel spreadsheet. It was then exported to Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22.0 for Windows software for analysis at $p < 0.5$. Analytical tools employed include descriptive statistics (means and frequencies), Bar Charts, Multiple Comparison, Range tests and Relative Importance Index (RII).

For a critical examination of the objectives of NHIS, the study identified the major goals stated in the NHIS policy statement and examined the extent to which the enrollees (beneficiaries/patients) agreed that the operations of the scheme actually addressed these goals. Ten statements were drawn up for examination as follows:

- Every Nigerian now has access to good health care services.
- The NHIS scheme has protected every Nigerian family from the financial hardship of huge medical bills;
- It has limited the rise in the cost of health care services in Nigeria;
- It has ensured an equitable distribution of health care costs among different income groups in Nigeria;
- The scheme has ensured the maintenance of high standard of health care delivery services;
- It has also ensured efficiency in health care services;
- The scheme has improved and harnessed private sector participation in the provision of health care services;
- It has ensured adequate distribution of health facilities within the Federation;
- The NHIS has ensured equitable patronage of all levels of health care; and
- The scheme has ensured the availability of funds to the health sector for improved services.

Responses from the ten statements were measured using a Likert Scale (Strongly Agreed, Agreed, Undecided, Disagreed, Strongly Disagreed) and were coded 5, 4, 3, 2, 1 respectively. These codes were used as weighting factors for the computation of weighted totals. These totals were divided by the respective sample sizes to obtain weighted average, also referred to as relative importance indices (RII), for each of the statements. The RII was used in ranking the statements and to generate the corresponding significant values.

$$\text{Weighted Total} = \sum f \dots\dots\dots (i)$$

$$\text{Relative Importance Index } (\bar{X}) = \sum f/n \dots\dots\dots (ii)$$

Enrollees' perspective on the operations of the scheme was examined alongside factors affecting the effectiveness of the programme.

Results

Sociodemographic characteristics of respondents showed that for every male enrollee in NHIS, there were about two females (31%: 69%). The age distribution revealed that the largest proportion of enrollees (55%) ranged between 30 and 49 years. Majority (75%) of the respondents were married. In terms of education, the largest group (70%) had basic tertiary education (between Advanced Levels and first degrees) while the smallest group (6.3%) had Masters Degrees or PhDs. Most of the respondents may be considered as sufficiently knowledgeable in social health insurance as over half (55%) had 6-10 years' experience with NHIS while another 22% had been receiving services for over a decade (Table 1). The mode of operations of the NHIS revealed that the most prominent point

of agreement among beneficiaries (85% agreed or strongly agreed) was that the scheme has ensured efficiency in healthcare services (Table 2). Most enrollees (76%) were of the opinion that NHIS ensured adequate distribution of healthcare facilities. Enrollees (73%) were generally satisfied with the NHIS strategy of pulling of funds/investments to drive the scheme. Majority (71%) either agreed or strongly agreed that the scheme has protected Nigerian families from catastrophic financial burdens of huge medical bills. These data need to be weighed against the finding that while 42% of enrollees were aware of the components of the NHIS, another 42% was unaware (Table 3). As high as 34% of enrollees were unsure whether NHIS has improved access to quality health care services as 65% could not access care at the nearest accredited facilities for medical emergencies (Table 4). In terms of the driving philosophy of the scheme, 66% of enrollees did not know that NHIS was meant to be private sector driven (Table 3) while 56% were unsure of whether the scheme has mobilized private sector participation in the provision of health care services. Most clients reported a significant level of satisfaction with the range and quality of services they received under the scheme. Only 28% felt the inadequacy of services was a serious factor while 39% felt otherwise (Table 5). Social health insurance as a healthcare financing mechanism requires a robust infrastructure backbone. Most enrollees (89.4%) identified poor infrastructure/equipment as the major bane of the NHIS (Table 5). Closely following the infrastructure deficit is the dearth of skilled manpower (83.7%) and poor manpower development programme (64.3%). Even though the enrollees were satisfied with the fund pooling strategy of NHIS, 66% of them still were of the opinion that poor funding exerts serious or very serious effects on the scheme. In Nigeria, the healthcare system is notorious for frequent industrial unrest and 66% of enrollees believe this exerts serious negative effects on the effectiveness of NHIS. A significant number of the enrollees thought that poor responsiveness by healthcare providers seriously affects the effectiveness of the NHIS. While 44.3% experience delays in issuance of identification and registration numbers, 57.3% had delays in issuance of their referral codes. About 60% rated the organisation of work by healthcare service providers as poor but only 26% saw the overall quality of care as low. Evidence from Focus Group Discussions revealed that certain trends were common among the three focus groups. The enrollees expressed that they were being faced with delay in the issuance of registration cards and referral codes, poor response and empathy of the workers. An excerpt from the responses given by the enrollees went thus;

“We must say NHIS has really been helpful. But the workers are not helping most times. After a very slow registration process, to even get referral code is like war. On two occasions, I had to keep calling the worker that would issue referral codes to me. I called up to 5 times before he could send it to me ... another problem with the scheme is the incessant out-of-stock syndrome. After drug prescriptions, the NHIS pharmacy is used to giving cheap drugs and telling us that the other drugs have finished ... apart from this, they need to add more services, especially laboratory tests, to the coverage of the scheme.”

One enrollee from FMC Abeokuta said

“It seems the scheme is faced with funding inadequacy. We experience delays in obtaining referral codes for emergencies. I hear there are delays and/or irregular payment of capitation fee and fee-for-service claims to the service providers. Aside all these, you can see there are significant shortages of personnel. Some of their equipment and infrastructure are dilapidated. We are also being faced with referral issues, out-of-pocket payment, registration delays, out-of-stock syndrome and exclusion of some services. If the NHIS handlers can help look into these, there will be less operational issues to contend with”

Discussants were asked, whether in their opinion, they thought that all the stakeholders were sufficiently carried along in the operations of the scheme? Their unanimous response across the three health facilities indicated that they were not sufficiently consulted and considered in the design, implementation and assessment of the NHIS.

Table 1: Socio-demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Variables	FMC Abeokuta		FMC Ebute Metta		UCH Ibadan		Total N (%)
	n	%	n	%	n	%	
Gender							
Male	32	32.0	28	28.0	33	33.0	93 (31.0)
Female	68	68.0	72	72.0	67	67.0	207 (69.0)
Age Groups							

Below 20	0	0.0	5	5.0	5	5.0	10 (3.3)
20 – 29	4	4.0	24	24.0	15	15.0	43 (14.3)
30 – 39	21	21.0	33	33.0	24	24.0	78 (26.0)
40 – 49	38	38.0	16	16.0	33	33.0	87 (29.0)
50 – 59	23	23.0	12	12.0	20	20.0	55 (18.3)
60 and above	14	14.0	10	10.0	3	3.0	27 (9.0)
Marital Status							
Single	29	29.0	10	10.0	24	24.0	63 (21.0)
Married	68	68.0	88	88.0	69	69.0	225 (75.0)
Others	3	3.0	2	2.0	7	7.0	12 (4.0)
Education							
Grade II	17	17.0	27	27.0	27	27.0	71 (23.7)
Cert/SSE/GCE							
O'Level							
A'Level/NCE/OND	48	48.0	39	39.0	28	28.0	115 (38.3)
D							
HND/Degree	32	32.0	28	28.0	35	35.0	95 (31.7)
Master/Ph.D.	3	3.0	6	6.0	10	10.0	19 (6.3)
Length of experience¹							
≤ 5 years	35	35.0	21	21.0	14	14.0	70 (23.3)
6 – 10 years	46	46.0	56	56.0	62	62.0	164 (54.7)
11 -15 years	14	14.0	12	12.0	20	20.0	46 (15.3)
≥ 15 years	5	5.0	11	11.0	4	4.0	20 (6.7)
<i>Total</i>	100	100	100	100	100	100	300 (100.0)

Abbreviations: FMC-Federal Medical Centre; UCH – University College Hospital; OND Ordinary National Diploma; HND- Higher National Diploma

Table 2: Enrollees' Assessment of the Objectives of NHIS (N=300)

<i>To what extent do you agree with the following statements about the objectives of NHIS?</i>	SA (f ₅)	A (f ₄)	UD (f ₃)	D (f ₂)	SD (f ₁)	Sig.	Σ	$\bar{X}$	Rank
Ensured efficiency in health care services	199 (66.3)	56 (18.7)	21 (7.0)	11 (3.7)	13 (4.3)	0.00	1317	4.39	1 st
Ensured adequate distribution of health facilities within the Federation	63 (21.0)	166 (55.3)	29 (9.7)	29 (9.7)	13 (4.3)	0.01	1137	3.79	2 nd
Protected every Nigerian family from the financial hardship of huge medical bills	78 (26.0)	135 (45.0)	18 (6.0)	55 (18.3)	14 (4.7)	0.01	1108	3.69	3 rd
Maintenance of high standard of health care delivery services	101 (33.7)	52 (17.3)	69 (23.0)	28 (9.3)	50 (16.7)	0.01	1026	3.42	4 th
Ensured the availability of funds to the health sector for improved services	91 (30.3)	29 (9.7)	89 (29.7)	35 (11.7)	56 (18.7)	0.02	964	3.21	5 th

Ensured an equitable distribution of health care costs among different income groups in Nigeria	37 (12.3)	121 (40.3)	29 (9.7)	88 (29.3)	25 (8.3)	0.02	957	3.19	6 th
Ensured equitable patronage of all levels of health care	55 (18.3)	87 (29.0)	36 (12.0)	100 (33.3)	22 (7.3)	0.02	953	3.18	7 th
Improved and harnessed private sector participation in the provision of health care services	23 (7.7)	56 (18.7)	169 (56.3)	19 (6.3)	33 (11.0)	0.03	917	3.06	8 th
Limited the rise in the cost of health care services in Nigeria	74 (24.7)	52 (17.3)	69 (23.0)	15 (5.0)	90 (30.0)	0.03	905	3.02	9 th
Every Nigerian now has access to good health care services	28 (9.3)	69 (23.0)	101 (33.7)	39 (13.0)	63 (21.0)	0.04	860	2.87	10 th

SA - Strongly Agree; A – Agree; UD - Undecided; D - Disagree; SD - Strongly Disagree; Σ - Weighted Total; $\bar{X}$ – Weighted Mean; Significant at $p < 0.05$ level

Table 3: Enrollees' Awareness of the Components of the NHIS ($N=300$)

<i>Awareness of Components of NHIS</i>	SA	A	D	SD	UD	Sig.
I am aware of the NHIS and its contents	53 (17.7)	74 (24.7)	47 (15.7)	25 (8.3)	101 (33.7)	0.00
The philosophy on which the NHIS is pivoted is private-sector driven	11 (3.7)	25 (8.3)	67 (22.3)	158 (52.7)	39 (13.0)	0.11
Government's position of administrator-regulator instead of owner-operator is considered appropriate for successful implementation	89 (29.7)	94 (31.3)	16 (5.3)	41 (13.7)	60 (20.0)	0.06
The objectives contained in the scheme are clearly spelt out and adequate for growth and development of the health sector	29 (9.7)	138 (46.0)	41 (13.7)	60 (20.0)	32 (10.7)	0.02
The focus on accessing, sensitization, processing, funding, utilization and marketing of health insurance in the scheme is quite in order	63 (21.0)	101 (33.7)	63 (21.0)	21 (7.0)	52 (17.3)	0.01
The emphasis on human resources development and capacity building as contained in the scheme is very crucial to successful implementation	169 (56.3)	17 (5.7)	52 (17.3)	32 (10.7)	30 (10.0)	0.03
Attention drawn on government's provision of adequate infrastructural facilities will guarantee smooth operations in the health sector	94 (31.3)	59 (19.7)	42 (14.0)	32 (10.7)	73 (24.3)	0.01

Emphasis placed on funding/investment in the health sector as contained in the scheme is a welcome development	203 (67.7)	17 (5.7)	35 (11.7)	41 (13.7)	4 (1.3)	0.00
Appropriate emphasis placed on research and development will guarantee successful implementation	72 (24.0)	63 (21.0)	101 (33.7)	25 (8.3)	39 (13.0)	0.02
The procedure for constant review of the scheme needs to be specified in the policy document	214 (71.3)	32 (10.7)	19 (6.3)	19 (6.3)	16 (5.3)	0.07

SA - Strongly Agreed; A – Agreed; UD - Undecided; D - Disagreed; SD - Strongly Disagreed; p <0.05

Table 4: Enrollees' Perspectives on Mode of Operations of HMOs regarding the Rights and Privileges of Beneficiaries/Enrollees (N=300)

<i>To what extent is an enrollee allowed to:</i>	SA	A	UN	D	SD	Sig.
Freely choose his/her accredited primary health care facility (ies)	63 (21.0)	28 (9.3)	178 (59.3)	12 (4.0)	19 (6.3)	0.00
Change primary health care facility after six (6) months with the present primary health care facility if he/she so desires?	79 (26.3)	84 (28.0)	67 (22.3)	41 (13.7)	29 (9.7)	0.01
Access care once the name is on the current NHIS enrollee register after proper identification?	81 (27.0)	127 (42.3)	63 (21.0)	9 (3.0)	20 (6.7)	0.00
Access treatment at the nearest NHIS accredited health care facilities on emergency presentations?	18 (6.0)	32 (10.7)	56 (18.7)	100 (33.3)	94 (31.3)	0.00
Add or remove dependant (s) subject to approval by NHIS?	114 (38.0)	59 (19.7)	67 (22.3)	12 (4.0)	48 (16.0)	0.01
Allowed to add extra dependant (s) on payment of a fee?	97 (32.3)	111 (37.0)	70 (23.3)	12 (4.0)	10 (3.3)	0.00

SA - Strongly Agreed; A – Agreed; UD - Undecided; D - Disagreed; SD - Strongly Disagreed; Σ - Weighted Total; $\bar{X}$ – Weighted Mean; p <0.05

Table 5: Enrollees' Perspectives on Factors Affecting NHIS operations (N=300)

<i>To what extent do the under listed factors affect the effectiveness of NHIS operations?</i>	No Effect	Very Little Effect	Moderate Effect	High Effect	Very High Effect
Delayed issuance of NHIS identity card and registration number to enrollees	4 (1.3)	74 (24.7)	89 (29.7)	100 (33.3)	33 (11.0)
Delayed issuance of referral codes to beneficiaries by HMOs	2 (1.0)	55 (18.3)	71 (23.7)	141 (47.0)	31 (10.3)
Industrial and social unrest	1 (0.0)	6 (2.0)	95 (31.7)	139 (46.3)	59 (19.7)
Poor/Inadequate funding	0 (0.0)	4 (1.3)	98 (32.7)	189 (63.0)	9 (3.0)
Lack of proper enlightenment of the enrollees at the point of registration on what services are covered (or not covered)	54 (18.0)	87 (29.0)	120 (40.0)	20 (6.7)	19 (6.3)

Inadequate level of infrastructural facilities, materials and equipment	4 (1.3)	9 (3.0)	19 (6.3)	206 (68.7)	62 (20.7)
Inadequate manpower (staffing)	0 (0.0)	2 (1.0)	47 (15.7)	219 (73.0)	32 (10.7)
Inadequate human capacity development (i.e. training and re-training of HCPs, HMO and NHIS staff members)	25 (8.3)	19 (6.3)	63 (21.0)	174 (58.0)	19 (6.3)
Out-of-pocket spending by enrollees due to non-availability of services or tests or procedures at the HCF level	11 (3.7)	32 (10.7)	124 (41.3)	62 (20.7)	71 (23.7)
Lack of access by enrollees to care outside their primary care provider even in cases of emergency?	10 (3.3)	26 (8.7)	147 (49.0)	69 (23.0)	48 (16.0)
Inefficient dispute resolution mechanisms among stakeholders (NHIS, HMOs, HCFs and enrollees) gone in resolving some of the challenges?	151 (50.3)	29 (9.7)	87 (29.0)	11 (3.7)	22 (7.3)
Inadequate protection of enrollees from abuse and avoidable harm (i.e. Safety)	84 (28.0)	36 (12.0)	47 (15.7)	58 (19.3)	75 (25.0)
Inadequate patients care, treatment and support services (i.e. Effectiveness and efficiency)	48 (16.0)	69 (23.0)	99 (33.0)	62 (20.7)	22 (7.3)
Poor staff involvement and treatment of patients with compassion, kindness, dignity and respect (i.e. poor attitude to care)	75 (25.0)	62 (20.7)	94 (31.3)	19 (6.3)	50 (16.7)
Poor organization of services so that they do not meet patient's needs (i.e. poor responsiveness)	22 (7.3)	39 (13.0)	58 (19.3)	105 (35.0)	76 (25.3)
Low Quality of care and services	58 (19.3)	101 (33.7)	63 (21.0)	19 (6.3)	59 (19.7)
Lack of transparency and accountability (i.e. Corruption)	0 (0.0)	21 (7.0)	84 (28.0)	113 (37.7)	82 (27.3)
Inadequate financial protection for enrollees	14 (4.7)	25 (8.3)	179 (59.7)	34 (11.3)	48 (16.0)
Lack of patient satisfaction with the services delivered	28 (9.3)	187 (62.3)	24 (8.0)	19 (6.3)	42 (14.0)

NHIS-National Health Insurance Scheme; HMO-Health Maintenance Organisations; HCF- Health care facilities

Discussion

The male to female ratio was about 1:2. Even though there has not been any similar previous evidence, this finding may be a reflection of the health-seeking behaviour of the different gender in Nigeria. The age distribution of the respondents fell between 20-59years. This is understandable given that a greater part of those currently employed in the formal public sector lie within that age bracket. Most of the respondents were of the opinion that NHIS Scheme was of immense benefit to them. This is in apparent agreement previous evidence that the NHIS has succeeded in saving many Nigerians from finance-related barriers in accessing quality health care (Onwujekwe, et al. 2019). However, 35% disagreed or strongly disagreed that the scheme has slowed down the rise in healthcare cost which affirms the claim by HMOs that limiting the rise in cost of healthcare represents the least achieved goal of the NHIS, a fact which has previously been attributed to low health insurance penetration (Adekola 2015). Some authors have expressed strong opinion that for the NHIS to achieve its objective of universal access to quality health care there would be urgent need for expansionary drive and more funding to establish more NHIS offices in health care facilities (Hao 2015). A survey of some service providers in Lagos State examined the

objectives of the NHIS and reported that the scheme had improved and harnessed private sector participation in the provision of health care services and ensured adequate distribution of health facilities within the federation (Adeniyi & Onajole 2010). It was also reported that the NHIS has harnessed private sector participation in the provision of health care services and many more corporate bodies were interested in partnering with the scheme (Mohammed 2015). Findings from this study show that enrollees cannot be said to agree with these claims. There seems to be a significant disconnect between the HMOs and enrollees on the mode of operation of the scheme as 22% of beneficiaries were unsure whether they could add or remove dependents subject to NHIS approval while only 30% knew they were allowed to freely choose accredited health care facilities (Table 4). As earlier reported by Ibe, et al. 2017; poor orientation and the attendant misinformation about NHIS left enrollees ignorant of the service coverage of the NHIS, which in turn affected their perception of the scheme. This contradicts the finding of this study, that 56% of enrollees agree or strongly agree that the objectives of NHIS are clearly spelt out and adequate for the growth and development of the health sector. The study showed that the mode of operations of the NHIS did not allow enrollees to access treatment at the nearest NHIS accredited health care facilities on emergency presentations. This has implications for avoiding complications in cases of emergencies. Over half of respondents (57.7%) reported they were free to add or remove dependents in consonance with earlier evidence which reported the flexibility in the modes of NHIS operations in that enrollees were allowed to add or remove dependents, subject to approval by the NHIS (Agba, Ushie, & Osuchuchwu 2010). The addition of such enrollees required extra payment though; the amount to be paid would be less than the amount hitherto paid by the original beneficiary. A related study underscored the need to allow the addition of enrollees (Odeyemi & Nixon 2013). For example, when a single (unmarried) NHIS beneficiary gets married, there is need for the spouse to be added. A newly married wife needs to be immediately added as NHIS beneficiary so that her antenatal, delivery and post-natal care could be adequately covered under the scheme. The need to allow the addition of one's spouse and children upon the payment of a specified extra amount of money has been well published (Odeyemi & Nixon 2013; Onyedibe, Goyit, & Nnadi, 2012). This confers same benefits on the original beneficiary and the new additions. An earlier report showed that sexual and reproductive health services were the most sought services among female enrollees of the NHIS in a health facility based assessment of the utilization of NHIS services by specific population groups (Odeyemi & Nixon 2013). Focus group discussants (enrollees) in the present study also acknowledged that they were provided with health and family planning education and choices. Family planning education was considered important in that it helps prevent unwanted pregnancy/births and by extension, helps prevent or reduce strain on health care facilities. The finding from this study on factors affecting operations of NHIS re-enforces previous evidence that inadequate human capacity development (i.e. training and re-training programmes for health care professionals, HMO and NHIS staff members) was partly responsible for the apparent ineffectiveness of the NHIS (Gustafsson-Wright & Schellekens 2013). Doctor-patient ratio in the sampled health care facilities was so high that patients reportedly had to wait for long hours before they could be attended to. The inadequate manpower in Nigerian health facilities have been previously discussed by various researchers (Olonade, et al.2019; Sparkes, et al. 2019; Adesina, 2019). The organisation of the healthcare services as well as the quality of services were identified by this study as poor. This finding is consistent with the view expressed in a similar study which identified sharp disparities on the perception of quality of care reported by the patients and the care givers (Adekola 2015). However, health system experts caution that though patients who were the beneficiaries of the services were likely to be honest, they would also possibly under-report effectiveness on the belief that they could be better served (Stuckler, et al. 2010). Healthcare facilities often experience out-of-stock syndrome for many essential medicines and supplies leading to avoidable out-of-pocket expenditures for 44.4% of enrollees who have to source these necessities elsewhere. Ordinarily, the NHIS operational guidelines entitle enrollees to drugs and equipment with only 10% of the cost payable by enrollees for full treatment until recovery (Ministry of Health 2013). Moreover, the inability to access care outside the primary healthcare providers, even after proper identification, was considered a serious setback by 39% of enrollees. Findings from the Focus Group Discussions were in agreement with previous evidence on patients' perceptions of the quality of service in general and the effectiveness of health insurance in particular (Odeyemi & Nixon 2013; Abiola, et al. 2019). However, discussants appreciated the importance of certain services they received under the scheme, including health and family planning education and choices, diagnostic tests as contained in the NHIS Diagnostic Test Lists, and certain consultation within the area of dental care and specific surgical operations. Earlier evidence reported that prescribed drugs and pharmaceutical care as contained in the NHIS Drugs List, in addition to preventive care including immunization (as applied in the National Programme on Immunisation) were made available to NHIS

enrollees (Osungbade, et al. 2014). These findings were supported by discussants. Further on the modes of operations of the NHIS, discussants acknowledged that in emergency cases, referral notifications were received within 48 hours as stipulated in the scheme. However, this finding falls short of best practices as seen when compared to the mode of operation of the health insurance in the United States where there were real time instant referral notifications of all referral operations (Odeyemi & Nixon 2013). In the United States and the United Kingdom, authorisation codes remained active until the patients were certified to have fully stabilized and completed all treatments (Onoka, et al. 2013).

Conclusion

National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS) activities were fairly understood by enrollees (patients), especially as it relates to ensuring equitable distribution of health care costs among different income groups in Nigeria. However, the mode of operation of the scheme was inadequate due to capacity limitations in terms of infrastructure, financial and human resources, inefficient management and poor responsiveness by service providers. Therefore, an urgent policy is needed to reform the NHIS in order to address these identified constraints.

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